

THE IMPORTANCE OF CLT IN TEACHING-LEARNING PROCESS

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Annotation: This article studies the role of communicative language teaching approach in education and for teaching and learning the English language. It is vital to mention that the work is devoted to highlight the effects of this technique to improve learners' speaking skill.

Keywords: Communicative language teaching (CLT), EFL classroom, interactive activities, the target language, an authentic way.

INTRODUCTION

There are many ways to help the students to improve their speaking skill. One of the ways is through communicative language teaching (CLT) approach. CLT is the approach in which the students are asked to use the language for communication in real situation. Applebaum states that using CLT will allow students the opportunity to use the target language in an authentic and meaningful way. The approach focuses on the students. The teacher organizes activities in such a way that the students can initiate and control the interaction. The teacher functions as a facilitator. According to Larsen-Freeman, the principles of CLT emphasize the importance of using a language to communicate in order to learn it. He stresses, "Being able to communicate requires more than linguistic competence; it requires communicative competence". Language (oral and written) functions to serve authentic purposes by facilitating meaningful communication.

The CEFR is the most comprehensive, and the most widely used set of foreign language education standards throughout the world. By describing the outcomes of a curriculum and its assessment in terms of what a learner can do in English, the CEFR encourages: 1 • the design of a communicative curriculum, • teachers teach communicatively, • the design of assessments that show a learner's communication skills. It is very important that the assessment matches the course so that it tests learners' communicative skills. As we can see from earlier descriptions of CEFR, the focus is on what a learner can do in communication. Therefore, logically, the learner is taught in a communicative way, linking his or her learning to the real world. CLT is at the heart of this approach in learning, teaching and assessment. CLT includes the following competences: Linguistic Competence – including grammar, vocabulary and pronunciation Pragmatic Competence – including function and discourse Sociolinguistic Competence – including politeness, register, etc. The ultimate aim will also be to make

graduates more employable by improving their communicative language capabilities.

What exactly is CLT? The methods and goals of CLT in classroom learning: - promote interaction with other speakers. - aim to involve and engage learners in the experience of communication. - provide learners with the linguistic key to open doors in society. What are the principles of CLT? Teaching language as communication Learning and competence are relative - not absolute Culture affects communicative competence Teachers use a variety of methodologies and techniques The more learners use the language, the more competent they become Learners are engaged in what they are doing So, the teacher and the learner need to understand that: we need to focus on how language is used in the real world. learners learn best when language is put in a meaningful context. language teaching and learning needs to be done in collaboration with the 'content' teacher CLT is learner-centered rather than teachercentered. error can be evidence of learning. we learn by doing, not by learning about doing. each teacher and each learner are individuals with different characteristic.

Advantages of CLT It's a holistic approach to language learning It's task-based so it provides an authentic context CLT develops critical thinking.

It motivates and engages learners It develops communicative competence It develops group dynamics and encourages teamwork It develops self-study skills and learner autonomy for life-long learning Authentic language' in real context should be introduced in the classroom whenever possible. It is the language used for day-today communication or functional purpose. There should be connectivity among all the language skills such as listening, speaking, reading and writing together since they are regularly used in real life. The target language is a vehicle for classroom communication, not just the object of study. Hence, attention should be given to teaching language for communication. One function may have different linguistic forms. Errors are tolerated and treated as a natural outcome of the development of communication skills. Proper situations should be created by the teacher so as to promote communication in the classroom. The social contexts of the communicative situations are essential for giving meaning to the utterances. The grammar and vocabulary that the students learn follow from the functions, situational context and the role of the interlocutors. The processes are as important as the forms. A method which aims at developing the capacity of the learners to communicate in a second language will focus at repeating continuously until they are able to communicate well in a target language. Communication is part and parcel of every human

being. When two or more people are conversing in day-to-day life, one may know something which is not known to the other. The purpose of the communication is to bridge this information gap. Another crucial feature of communication is that the learners have option, both in terms of what they will say and, more particularly, how they will say it. This process is implicit in the above two processes. When two persons take part in an interaction, there is normally some aim behind communicating and in what way other person reacts is evaluated in terms of that aim. As explained in the key concepts section there are four main characteristics that constitute a task: (1) meaning is primary; (2) there is a goal which needs to be worked towards; (3) task completion has some priority; and (4) there is a real-world relationship. Using the lesson from Homework Task One, explain if you use a true 'task' in the lesson. Thus, how does the task you identify use the four main characteristics? If not, please create a task that can be used for your Homework Task One and explain how it is a task using the four main characteristics. According to Richards the TBL framework consists of three main phrases, provides 3 basic conditions for language learning. These are pre-task, task -cycle and language focus² . The pre-task stage involves the teacher providing instructions about the task and having the class brainstorm any useful vocabulary that the learners may already know which could help them during the task. The purpose of the pre-task is to activate student's own linguistic resources to prepare them for the task cycle. The task cycle consists of learners participating in the main task groups, pairs or individually, depending on whether the task is interactive. In the task cycle the learners use their existing linguistic skills to complete the task while the teacher serves as a facilitator, only providing assistance when necessary. On completing the task-cycle, each group collectively prepares a report on its findings and presents the report to the rest of the class, with the teacher only commenting as needed. Finally in the language focus part of the lesson, students are directed towards analyzing the language forms used during the task. Task-based language teaching method. is a student centered approach to teach foreign languages. It is an offshoot of the communicative instruction where activities focus on having students use authentic target language in order to complete meaningful tasks and situations. They might meet by chance in the real life and other project-based assignments. These project activities could include the tasks which conducting an interview in order to find answers to specific questions or gathering information to make a poster or advertisement. In task-based teaching the centre of the learning process moves to the students themselves and allows them to come to the

realization that language is a tool to tackle and solve real-life problems. TBLT helps students how to ask questions, how to negotiate meaning and how to interact. When creating the task I firstly pay attention to the proper use of meaning. Students should know the meaning of the words in the task. Here it should be given to the priority of the CLT. Students have to understand in what competence, words of the task given. The main goal of any task is learning from the task. Tasks may be designed so that they should keep learning characters and they should have certain priorities. The tasks should be connected with real – life situations.

CONCLUSION

In short, communicative language teaching makes use of real-life situations that necessitate communication. The teacher sets up a situation that students are likely to encounter in real life. The communicative language teaching approach can leave students in suspense as to the outcome of a class exercise, which will vary according to their reactions and responses. The real-life simulations change from day to day. Students' motivation to learn comes from their desire to communicate in meaningful ways about meaningful topics. For those reasons the writer is interested in discussing whether the information-gap and role-play speaking activity as a part of CLT are good to apply in teaching speaking and how the procedure of teaching speaking using those techniques.

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